

The Moderating Role of Marital Status in the Effect of Psychological Ownership on Organizational Identification Mediated by Presenteeism

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Abstract

This study investigates whether marital status shapes the association between psychological ownership and organizational identification, considering presenteeism as an intervening mechanism. A survey was conducted with 386 employees working in various health institutions in Konya. The instruments were validated through exploration factor analysis and reliability analyses. Hypotheses were tested using Hayes' PROCESS Macro framework. Findings revealed that psychological ownership significantly contributes to organizational identification. The results further indicate a conditional indirect effect through presenteeism. In addition, marital status was found to significantly moderate this indirect effect, indicating a moderated mediation relationship.

Key words: Psychological Ownership, Organizational Identification, Presenteeism, Moderating Role of Marital Status

JEL Code: M10, J24, M54, D23, I12,

1. Introduction

Psychological ownership reflects a state in which individuals feel that the work, object or organization belongs to them. This feeling is related to individuals expressing the related object or relationship as "mine" or "ours". Therefore, it is related to individuals' seeing themselves as a part of the organization and having a say in decision-making processes related to the organization (Avey, Avolio, Crossley & Luthans, 2009). When psychological ownership is considered from an organizational perspective, it is related to individuals' combining organizational goals with personal goals and seeing themselves as a part of the organization and the sense of belonging that employees feel to the organization. Therefore, having

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control over the organization contributes positively to the sense of ownership (Pierce, Kostova & Dirks, 2001). Knowing one's organization well enables the employee to associate his/her identity with the organization (Baxter, Aurisicchio, & Childs, 2015). The sub-dimensions of psychological ownership are discussed by Pierce et al. (2001) under three headings: effectiveness-efficiency, self-identity and sense of belonging.

In cases where employees do not feel psychological ownership, it is expected to diminish their levels of presenteeism. Presenteeism represents a critical organizational challenge where employees exhibit low performance and reduced productivity at work due to underlying health problems or psychological conditions. This systematic condition may lead to employees feeling excluded or perceived as worthless within the organization. Presence at work encompasses employees' desire to fulfill and contribute at work. According to Kahn (1990), it is when employees connect all their feelings and thoughts to the roles represented by the job within the framework of the here and now logic. Presenteeism has an indirect effect on organizational identification. Individuals who work with low performance may have fewer ties with the organization and their sense of belonging (Miraglia & Johns, 2016). Employees with high psychological ownership will not avoid taking more responsibility in their workplaces, but the connection between psychological ownership and organizational identification may weaken because of some negative experiences that employees have in their workplaces. One of these factors is lack of presence at work (Mayhew, Ashkanasy, Bramble & Gardner, 2007).

As a result, both presenteeism and psychological ownership may affect employees' sense of organizational identification. Employees who do not feel worthless or belong may have difficulty in identifying organizational goals with personal goals. The more individuals see themselves as a part of the organization and feel its existence, the stronger their identification with the organization. As a result, organizational identification is the process of integration and harmonization of employees' goals and organizational goals (Asforth & Mael, 1989). Therefore, within the scope of this study, the relationship between these variables will be discussed together with marital status. Because marital status can affect employees' workplace experiences in different ways.

2. Literature Review

In today's business world, the psychological bond that employees establish with their organizations is expected to directly affect job performance, motivation and organizational commitment (Pierce, Kostova & Dirks, 2001). While employees with a high sense of ownership may tend to take more responsibility and identify with their organizations, this positive effect may decrease when they are exposed to the situation of not presenteeism (Mayhew et al., 2007). This work explores how marital status might influence the connection between psychological ownership and organizational identification by considering the role of presenteeism. By addressing this relationship, the research seeks to provide insights that can enhance

understanding of employee commitment processes and guide human resource policies that better account for individual differences in the workplace.

Psychological Ownership

According to Pierce, Kostova and Dirks (2001), psychological ownership is the development of a sense of ownership over an object or space. Therefore, unlike physical or legal ownership, this concept is a state of ownership shaped in the inner world of the individual. Employees' feeling of psychological ownership towards their organizations and jobs leads to positive outcomes such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment and increased performance (Avey et.al., 2009; Mayhew et al., 2007). It also enables individuals to generate innovative ideas and contribute to the organization (Brown et al., 2005).

Psychological ownership is about an individual having control over an idea, organization or anything else. When individuals feel psychological ownership, they take more responsibility in the organization and contribute to the organization (Van Dyne & Pierce, 2004). However, because of psychological ownership, some employees may resist organizational change or have difficulty in developing cooperation with other employees due to the development of a sense of excessive ownership of the organization (Pierce et al., 2001).

There are many organizational theories that support psychological ownership. The concept will be discussed in terms of self-identity theory, spatial commitment theory and embeddedness theory.

Self-identity Theory was developed by American sociologist Sheldon Stryker in the 1970s. The theory is about individuals constructing their sense of self by associating with certain objects, ideas or organizations (Dittmar, 1992). In this context, the foundation of psychological ownership is laid when the individual sees himself/herself as a part of the organization, field or idea. According to Pierce and colleagues (2001), individuals define their identities through the objects or roles they possess, and psychological appropriation is strengthened at the end of this process.

The Spatial Connectedness Theory was proposed by Low & Altman (1992) and developed by Scannell & Gifford (2010). When individuals feel a certain place as their own, it develops a sense of belonging, which increases their desire to protect, develop or stay there (Manzo & Perkins, 2006). Employees can develop psychological ownership by adding personal objects to their workspaces or organizing some areas according to themselves (Brown, Lawrence & Robinson, 2005).

The Endowment Theory was proposed by Thaler (1980) and developed by Kahneman, Ketsch and Thaler (1991). The theory is about individuals being exposed to a certain object or situation and feeling a psychological ownership towards this situation or object because of spending time with it (Beggan, 1992).

The feeling of psychological ownership may increase because of employees being in the same workplace for a long time, taking active roles in some projects or taking responsibility for business processes (Brown et al., 2005). Individuals prefer not to lose something they must gain an equivalent gain (Tversky & Kahneman, 1991).

Presenteeism at Work

The concept of presenteeism is the presence of employees at work when they are physically or mentally unable to be as productive as desired (Johns, 2010). In traditional personnel management, presenteeism was important, but in recent years, human resource management has been very interested in presenteeism (Miraglia & Johns, 2016). In the literature, this concept is considered as the loss of productivity because of employees coming to work despite being sick, exhausted or demotivated (Hemp, 2004).

Although the concept of presenteeism is informed by many theoretical frameworks, it will be in terms of resource conservation theory, the job demands-resources model and social change theory.

The Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, proposed by Hobfoll (1989), is about the tendency of individuals to conserve their physical, mental and emotional resources, which is why employees continue to go to work despite being sick or exhausted due to reasons such as the fear of losing their existing jobs, falling behind in their careers, and increasing their workload (Demerouti et al., 2009). However, if this situation lasts for a long time, it may lead to the depletion of individual resources and some health problems. According to Schaufeli & Greenglass (2001), burnout is a state of physical, mental and emotional exhaustion resulting from prolonged exposure to working conditions that require emotional labor (as cited in Yürür, 2011).

The Job Demands-Resources Model (JD-R Model) was developed by Bakker & Demerouti (2007). The theory refers to the balance between employees' workloads and their socio-psychological resources. Accordingly, employees experience psychological and physical burnout due to high job expectations. The lack of a work environment that supports employees in organizations may cause them to underperform despite being at work, that is, they may not be present at work (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

Social Exchange Theory, Blau (1964) argues that the psychological contracts that employees sign with their workplaces affect their work behaviors. Employees may exhibit presenteeism behaviors according to the support they receive from their organizations and the organizational culture. For example, in workplaces where job retention guarantees are low, job performance is constantly monitored and presenteeism is frowned upon, employees may see going to work as an obligation despite being sick (Johns, 2010).

Organizational Identification

The cognitive and emotional bond that an individual establishes with his/her organization is referred to as "organizational identification" (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). When employees see their organization as a part of their identity, they perceive organizational achievements as their own achievements (Dutton, Dukerich & Harquail, 1994). This situation causes employees to embrace the organization and develop positive attitudes towards the organization. Although organizational identification is mostly associated with social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1986) in academic studies, it has been positively related to positive outcomes such as organizational commitment, job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior (Van Knippenberg & Sleebos, 2006).

Although the concept of organizational identification is supported by many theories, it will be discussed in terms of social identity theory, self-conceptualization theory and self-determination theory.

Social Identity Theory, developed by Henri Tajfel & John Turner in the 1970s, argues that individuals develop a sense of belonging to the communities to which they belong and that this sense of belonging affects individuals' self-perceptions Tajfel & Turner (1986). In organizational terms, employees' perception of their organization as a part of their social identity forms the basis of organizational identification.

Self-Conceptualization Theory, developed by Brewer & Gardner (1996), addresses the individual's self-concept at three levels. These are individual self, relational self and collective self. Organizational identification is handled at the level of collective self and explains the bond that individuals establish with their organizations.

Self-Determination Theory, developed by Deci & Ryan (1985), explains the intrinsic motivation of individuals and argues that meeting employees' needs for autonomy, competence and relationship building increases organizational identification (Gagné & Deci, 2005).

Development of Hypotheses

Psychological ownership refers to employees' sense of possession, belonging, and responsibility toward their organization. Previous studies have demonstrated that psychological ownership positively affects employees' motivation, engagement, and workplace attitudes (Avey et al., 2009). Employees with high levels of psychological ownership tend to feel more emotionally connected to their organizations and demonstrate stronger involvement in organizational processes. In this context, psychological ownership may reduce presenteeism by increasing employees' psychological attachment and commitment to work.

H1: Psychological ownership negatively affects presenteeism.

Van Dyne, & Pierce (2004) found that psychological ownership structurally decreases individuals' experiences of presenteeism. According to the results of the research, employees stated that when they felt psychological ownership, they experienced more organizational participation and felt more valuable. Özdemir and Demirci (2021) also found a negative correlation between organizational commitment and presenteeism. According to Kahn (1990), presenteeism may weaken employees' emotional attachment and organizational identification. Organizational identification of individuals experiencing this situation may be negatively affected (Ashforth & Mael, 1989).

H2: Presenteeism negatively affects organizational identification.

Organizational identification is the state in which employees see themselves as a part of the organization, identify with the values of the organization and contribute to the organization. Dutton, Dukerich & Harquail (1994) found that psychological ownership increases employees' work motivation and job performance.

H3: Psychological ownership positively affects organizational identification.

Within this framework, the first three hypotheses of the study were developed to test the direct relationships among the variables with support from literature. To examine indirect effects, marital status was included as a moderator variable, and the study aimed to contribute to the literature by examining these relationships.

H4: Marital status moderates the relationship between psychological ownership and presenteeism.

H5: Marital status moderates the relationship between presenteeism and organizational identification.

H6: Presenteeism mediates the relationship between psychological ownership and organizational identification.

H7: Marital status moderates the indirect effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification through presenteeism.

3. Methodology

This section provides details about the research model, measurement tools, study population, sample, and data analysis. The study focused on examining

whether marital status moderates the relationship between psychological ownership and organizational identification, considering presenteeism as a mediating factor. Within this framework, the direct and indirect effects of psychological ownership on presenteeism and organizational identification were assessed. In addition, the moderating role of marital status in these relationships was evaluated.

Population and Sample

According to statistics from the Ministry of Health, data on the number of personnel working in health institutions were used to define the study population. The study included employees who voluntarily provided informed consent to participate and agreed for their data to be used for scientific purposes. The sample was determined through a simple random sampling method, and data were collected face-to-face to encourage participation. Since it was not possible to fully reach the entire research population, the sample size was calculated as 384 participants, based on a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error.

This sample size is considered sufficient to represent a population of approximately 10,000,000 individuals (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2018:130). The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Findings

Features	Variables	F	%
Gender	Male	108	28
	Woman	278	72
Marital Status	Married	311	80,6
	Single	75	19,4
Employment Status	Health personnel	282	73,1
	Other Personnel	104	26,9
Level of education	Primary-Secondary education	99	25,6
	Associate degree	104	26,9
	Bachelor - Master's degree	183	47,4
Total		386	100

As shown in Table 172% of the employees who participated in the study were female, 80.6% were married, 73.1% were health personnel and 47.4% had bachelor's or master's degrees

Research Model

The purpose of this study is to determine the moderating role of marital status in the effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification through presenteeism. While there may be many mediators explaining the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the degree of this effect may

vary according to the marital status of individuals. In this study, it is thought that the psychological ownership levels of healthcare workers affect their organizational identification through presenteeism. It is also assumed that the marital status of the employees affects this relationship. The conceptual model to be tested in the study is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model (Model 58)

Data Collection Tools

In this research, employees' psychological ownership levels were assessed using the scale originally developed by Van Dyne and Pierce (2004), which comprises seven items under a single dimension. The Turkish version of the scale was taken from the adaptation study conducted by Demirkaya and Kandemir (2014). The five-point Likert-type scale includes six positively worded items and one negatively worded item. Organizational identification was evaluated through the scale created by Mael and Ashforth (1992), consisting of six items and originally designed as a seven-point Likert scale. In its Turkish adaptation by Tak and Aydemir (2004), as referenced by Telman and Aşkun Çelik (2013), the scale was applied using a five-point Likert format. Presenteeism levels were measured with the "Stanford Presenteeism Scale," developed by Koopman et al. (2002), which includes six items. The scale's Turkish adaptation and validation were carried out by Dalkılıç (2017). This unidimensional scale also uses a five-point Likert response format.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using the 22nd version of the SPSS program. Skewness and kurtosis coefficients were examined to assess whether the data were normally distributed. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted to evaluate structural validity, and Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was calculated to assess reliability. Hypotheses were tested using the Process Macro program, an add-on developed by Hayes for SPSS. This program facilitated mediator and moderator

analyses, with results evaluated through models that used confidence intervals obtained via the Bootstrap method (95% confidence level), ensuring more valid and reliable findings (Gürbüz, 2019).

In this framework, the 58th model of the Process Macro program was applied to jointly assess the mediating and moderating effects. The mediating variable represents the factor explaining how and why the relationship between the independent and dependent variables occurs, while the moderating variable reflects the factor influencing the strength of this relationship (Gürbüz, 2019).

Structural Validity and Reliability Analyses of the Scales

At the initial stage of the study, the data were assessed for normality. The skewness and kurtosis values for the organizational identification scale (-0.150 and -0.027, respectively), the work presenteeism scale (1.034 and 1.419), and the psychological ownership scale (-0.322 and -0.079) all fall within the acceptable range of -1.5 to +1.5, indicating that the data approximate a normal distribution (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). After confirming normality, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed to examine the construct validity of the measurement tools employed in the study.

In this study, the structural validity of the measurement tools was examined through an exploratory factor analysis using the principal component method with direct oblimin rotation. The reliability of the scales was evaluated through Cronbach's Alpha, a widely accepted method for measuring internal consistency in social sciences (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2018).

The analysis showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value for the psychological ownership scale was 0.789, and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the data were appropriate for factor analysis. Components with eigenvalues greater than 1 were retained, revealing a unidimensional seven-item structure that accounted for 66.10% of the total variance. All item factor loadings exceeded 0.40, and the internal consistency of the scale, measured by Cronbach's Alpha, was 0.903.

For the organizational identification scale, the KMO value was 0.644, and Bartlett's test was also significant ($p < 0.001$). Exploratory factor analysis identified a single-factor structure for the six-item scale, which explained 43.78% of the total variance. Factor loadings for all items were above 0.32, and Cronbach's Alpha for this scale was 0.683, confirming its reliability (Kayış, 2010). For a presenteeism scale, KMO was 0.658 and Bartlett's test was significant ($p < 0.001$). The single factor of the scale explained 58.41% of the variance and the factor loadings were above 0.40. Cronbach's alpha value is 0.795.

According to the results of the validity and reliability analyses, it is possible to say that the psychological ownership, organizational identification and presenteeism scales used in the study are valid and reliable scales.

Testing Hypotheses

In the study, Process Macro's model number 58 developed by Hayes was preferred to test the hypotheses (for SPSS). In the program that uses the bootstrap approach (95%) in regulatory and mediating effect analyses, if the confidence interval does not cover zero, the hypotheses are considered to be confirmed (Hayes & Preacher, 2014).

In order to test the moderating role of marital status in the effect of psychological ownership levels of healthcare workers on organizational identification through presenteeism, the results of the regression analysis conducted using the Process Macro program based on the bootstrap technique are given below. First, the results of the model with data on the relationship between psychological ownership, job presence and marital status variables are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Regression Analysis Results Related to the Effect of Psychological Ownership on Presenteeism

	<i>b</i>	SE	t	p	LLCU	ULCI
Dependent Variable: Presenteeism						
Psychological Ownership (X)	0.082	0.173	0.477	0.633	-,2570	,4217
Marital Status (W)	1.341	0.476	2.814	0.005	0.404	2.278
X.W.	-0.408	0.139	-2.934	0.003	-0.681	-0.134
Conditional Effect= Marital Status						
Married	-0.325	0.059	-5.506	.000	-0.442	-0.209
Single	-0.733	0.126	-5.826	.000	-0.980	-0.486

R= 0.379, R²= 0.144, n=386, p <0.001

According to the findings in Table 2, the model examining the effect of psychological ownership on presenteeism was found to be statistically significant. All variables used in the regression analysis explained 14% of the variance in presenteeism (R² = 0.144). However, the results of the analysis show that the direct effect of psychological ownership on presenteeism is not significant (b = 0.082; 95% CI [-0.2570, 0.4217], t = 0.477; p > 0.05). Therefore, hypothesis **H1 was not supported**. On the other hand, the effect of marital status on presenteeism was significant (b = 1.341; 95% CI [0.404, 2.278], t = 2.814; p < 0.05). Moreover, the interaction between psychological ownership and marital status was found to be significant and it was concluded that it had a moderating effect on presenteeism (b = -.408; 95% CI [-.681; -.134], t = -2.934; p < 0.05). **Therefore, H4 was supported**. The slope graph in Figure 1 reveals this effect more clearly.

Figure 2. The Moderating Role of Marital Status

When the moderating effect of marital status is analyzed, the effect of psychological ownership on presenteeism differs between married and single employees. The effect of psychological ownership on presenteeism is significant for both married ($b = -0.325$; 95% CI [-0.442, -0.209]; $t = -5.506$, $p < 0.05$) and single healthcare workers ($b = -0.733$; 95% CI [-0.980, -0.486]; $t = -5.828$, $p < 0.05$). However, the negative effect of psychological ownership on the presenteeism levels of single healthcare workers ($b = -0.733$) was almost two times stronger than its effect on the presenteeism levels of married healthcare workers ($b = -0.325$).

The results of the model with data on the relationship between the variables of presenteeism, marital status and organizational identification are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Regression Analysis Results Related to the Effect of Presenteeism on Organizational Identification

	<i>b</i>	SE	t	p	LLCU	ULCI
Dependent Variable: Organizational Identification						
Psychological Ownership (X)	0.352	0.043	8.277	0.001	0.269	0.436
Presenteeism (M)	-0.337	0.108	-3.113	0.002	-0.550	-0.124
Marital Status (W)	-0.647	0.230	-2.808	0.005	-1.099	-0.194
Int (M.W)	0.256	0.083	3.082	0.002	0.093	0.419
Conditional Effect= Marital Status						
Married (1)	-0.0812	0.042	-1.939	0.053	-0.163	0.001
Single (2)	0.175	0.075	2.339	0.020	0.028	0.321

$R = 0.433$, $R^2 = 0.189$, $n = 386$, $p < 0.001$

The analysis indicated that the overall model explains 18.9% of the variance in organizational identification. Psychological ownership had a significant positive direct effect on organizational identification ($b = 0.352$; $p < 0.05$), confirming that **Hypothesis 3 (H3) was supported**. Conversely, presenteeism demonstrated a negative and significant influence on organizational identification ($b = -0.337$; $p < 0.05$). These findings indicate that **Hypothesis 2 (H2) was supported**. Marital status also had a significant effect ($b = -0.647$; $p < 0.05$) and further moderates the relationship between presenteeism and organizational identification ($b = 0.256$; $p < 0.05$). This outcome supports the assumption that marital status influences how presenteeism relates to organizational identification, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 3. Moderating Role of Marital Status (Slope Graph)

When the moderating effect of marital status is examined, the effect of presenteeism on organizational identification differs between married and single employees. The effect of presenteeism on organizational identification is statistically insignificant for married employees ($b = -0.081$; 95% CI [-0.163, 0.001]; $t = -1.939$, $p > 0.05$). The effect of presenteeism on organizational identification is statistically significant in single health care workers ($b = 0.175$; 95% CI [0.028, 0.321]; $t = 2.340$, $p < 0.05$). While the effect of presenteeism on organizational identification was insignificant in married employees, this effect was found to be statistically significant in single employees.

In the final stage of the analysis, conditional indirect effects and an integrated moderated mediation model were examined. The findings indicated that the direct effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification was

positive and significant ($b = 0.353$, 95% CI [0.269, 0.436], $p < 0.001$). When examining the conditional indirect effects of psychological ownership on organizational identification via presenteeism, the confidence intervals for married (Effect = 0.026, 95% bootstrap CI [-0.011, 0.066]) and single employees (Effect = -0.128, 95% bootstrap CI [-0.262, 0.000]), the confidence intervals included or were close to zero, indicating that the indirect effects at the subgroup level were not significant on their own. However, according to Hayes's (2015) approach, the primary assessment is based on the Modified Mediation Index, which tests for differences between subgroups. In this regard, the index was determined to be significant (Index = -0.154, 95% bootstrap CI [-0.286, -0.020]). The fact that the confidence interval excludes zero indicates that the indirect effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification via presenteeism differs significantly according to marital status. Thus, while **Hypothesis 5 (H5) was supported** through the moderation analysis, the significant moderated mediation index and conditional indirect effect findings provided empirical **support for Hypothesis 6 (H6) and Hypothesis 7 (H7)**.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification, the mediating role of presenteeism in this relationship and the moderating effect of marital status were examined. The findings show that psychological ownership has a significant relationship with organizational identification and this relationship differs depending on the level of presenteeism. In addition, marital status is a determining factor in this process and there are different interaction dynamics between married and single employees. These findings will be evaluated in the light of the relevant literature and suggestions will be presented to increase the sense of ownership in the organizational context. Conclusions and discussions obtained because of research findings:

Psychological ownership has no direct impact on work presenteeism

Psychological ownership means that employees identify themselves with a particular group, idea or value. When employees feel ownership of their workplace and are connected to the organization, their job satisfaction and performance may increase, but this situation alone will not be decisive on employees' absence at work. While psychological ownership is expected to affect employees' commitment and work relationships, it may not have a direct impact on existential problems in work life. This effect is more related to employee motivation, job satisfaction and sense of identification (Ötken, 2015; Işık & Uçar, 2019). Therefore, although psychological ownership is an important concept in business life, it cannot explain the lack of presence at work alone. While psychological ownership encourages employees' engagement at work, its impact on presenteeism depends on moderating factors such as general stress level or health indicators (Biron, Karanika-Murray, & Ivers, 2022; Carmeli, Reiter-Palmon, & Ziv, 2010). Psychological ownership, taken

together with positive workplace variables, may reduce employee presenteeism, but it has no direct effect in isolation. According to Dietz, Zacher, Scheel, Otto, & Rigotti (2020), psychological ownership indirectly affects presenteeism through job satisfaction by increasing employees' intrinsic motivation.

The effect of presenteeism on organizational identification is negative

Even if employees are physically present at work, reduced functioning associated with presenteeism may negatively affect organizational identification. The effect of presenteeism on organizational identification is expected to be negative. Not being present at work weakens employees' organizational commitment and identification (Caverley, Cunningham & MacGregor, 2007). When individuals feel worthless or inadequate in the work environment, their ties with the organization weaken. This situation may negatively affect employees' commitment to the goals and values of the organization. Meriç et al. (2018) examined the relationship between teachers' presenteeism and organizational identification levels and found a positive and significant relationship between presenteeism and organizational identification. However, the direction of this relationship may vary depending on occupational context and sample characteristics. Braakman-Jansen et al. (2012) found that reduced work functioning associated with presenteeism decreases employees' productivity and performance. Presenteeism can reduce employees' motivation, job satisfaction and productivity. This kind of emotional disconnection makes it difficult for employees to see themselves as part of the organization and consequently reduces organizational identification. Therefore, organizations should provide a supportive environment to help their employees cope with such feelings.

The effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification is positive

Psychological ownership positively affects organizational identification by increasing employees' sense of belonging and ownership in their workplaces. According to Avey et.al. (2009), psychological ownership plays a mediating role in increasing employee engagement and organizational identification. Employees' sense of ownership supports identification by increasing active participation in work processes (Van Dyne & Pierce, 2004). When employees see themselves as a part of the work or organization, they become more attached to the organization. This situation increases employees' organizational identification. Psychological ownership is the main driving force of organizational identification by facilitating emotional bonding with the organization (Pierce & Jussila, 2011).

Marital status has a moderating role in the effect of psychological ownership on work presenteeism

Individuals who are married or have children may feel more pressure at work due to family responsibilities. Married employees may experience higher levels of stress due to competing responsibilities, and this may increase levels of presenteeism at work. Coşkun (2012) found that married employees experience

higher levels of presenteeism at work than single employees. Mohammadi, Darbani & Parsakia (2021) found that marital responsibilities are associated with increased job stress and affect overall job performance. Ertürk & Erdirençelebi (2017) found that married academics experience more problems of non-presence at work. Canbaz (2021) did not find a significant relationship between the problem of not being present at work and marital status. Similarly, Uysal, Ak, and Yılmaz Kılıçkaya (2024) reported that single healthcare employees exhibited higher levels of presenteeism compared to married employees. These findings suggest that the relationship between marital status and presenteeism may vary across occupational context and sample characteristics. The effect of psychological ownership on this relationship should be evaluated in interaction with marital status, which emphasizes the need to develop supportive strategies in the workplace. From the other perspective, single individuals may also face different challenges, especially factors such as lack of social support systems or feelings of loneliness, which may negatively affect the sense of presence at work. Consequently, marital status may influence individuals' organizational identification by establishing a complex relationship between psychological ownership and experiences related to presenteeism. Therefore, organizations should develop supportive individual policies considering the different life circumstances of their employees.

Marital status has a moderating role in the effect of presenteeism on organizational identification

The marital status variable can shape individuals' experiences at work by affecting their social and emotional needs, responsibilities and support networks. Individuals who are married or have children may feel work stress more intensely due to family responsibilities. This may increase their sense of not being present at work and negatively affect their organizational identification. Family support and social networks can help these individuals cope with stress, but sometimes family pressures can also reduce job satisfaction. On the other hand, single employees may experience difficulties such as lack of social support or loneliness. This may prevent them from feeling valued and reduce their organizational identification. Studies (Akbar, Ahmad, Ali, and Naz, 2019; Freeling, Rainbow, & Chamberlain, 2020) have shown that organizational support and fairness moderate presenteeism and related outcomes, and suggest that demographic variables, including marital status, can further improve these relationships. These effects are more pronounced in high-stress occupations such as health care, where personal circumstances interact heavily with workplace behaviors. Marital status may shape outcomes for individuals in the work environment by moderating the impact of feeling presenteeism on organizational identification. Organizations should create an inclusive and supportive organizational environment, taking into account the different marital statuses of employees.

Psychological ownership has a conditional indirect effect on organizational identification through presenteeism depending on marital status

While psychological ownership strengthens individuals' bonds with the organization, presenteeism may negatively affect this process. If an individual does not feel present in the organization, this may weaken his/her organizational identification. Therefore, absence at work may indirectly hinder the positive effects of psychological ownership. Although there are no academic studies directly addressing this hypothesis, studies on psychological ownership show that it promotes positive organizational outcomes such as identification by encouraging an individual's sense of responsibility and belonging (Pierce & Jussila, 2011; Avey et.al., 2009).

Presenteeism, which is characterized by reduced productivity despite being physically present at work, can negatively affect an employee's organizational identification due to reduced interaction and alignment with organizational values. However, in some cases, when the sense of psychological ownership is very strong, individuals are better able to cope with challenges and overcome presenteeism. In this context, the indirect effect of psychological ownership may vary from situation to situation. In conclusion, the effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification has a complex relationship and although presenteeism is expected to have a significant effect in this relationship, the model explains 14.4% of the dependent variable (presenteeism). These findings indicate that the model has limited explanatory power.

Marital status moderates the indirect effect of psychological ownership on organizational identification through presenteeism

Marital status may affect individuals' organizational experiences in different ways, but it may not always be a determining factor. For example, some individuals may develop a strong sense of psychological ownership regardless of their marital status, which may positively affect their workplace commitment and organizational identification. In such cases, the employee's feeling of inadequacy at work may not differ according to marital status. The organizational identification levels of married and single individuals may differ depending on the feeling of not being present at work. In order to increase organizational identification, organizations should implement practices that reduce presenteeism and strengthen psychological ownership (Avey et.al., 2009; Van Dyne & Pierce, 2004; Brown, Lawrence & Robinson, 2005). In this research model, 18.9% of the dependent variable (organizational identification) is explained. This shows that the model has a medium level of explanatory power. Organizational identification is more positively associated among single employees with lower levels of presenteeism. Married individuals are usually more preoccupied with family responsibilities, and this may affect their organizational identification. Since single individuals are less affected by domestic responsibilities, they may be more interested in their workplace and focus on work processes more easily and thus may experience higher organizational identification. When single employees feel that they cannot be

present at work, they strive to change the situation. This effort increases their sense of organizational identification and reduces presenteeism.

Recommendations

The sustainable success of organizations is directly related to employees' work engagement and work performance. Employees' physical and psychological engagement in their jobs is of great importance for job satisfaction and organizational productivity. However, presenteeism, lack of organizational identification and low levels of psychological ownership can negatively affect employee motivation and productivity. Therefore, organizations and managers should develop some strategies to improve these factors.

What to Do to Increase Organizational Identification

Organizational identification occurs when employees see themselves as a part of their organizations and internalize the values of the organization and their own values (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). A strong bond between employees and their organizations increases their job satisfaction and job performance and decreases their turnover intentions (Riketta, 2005). Therefore, it is very important for managers to adopt policies that will strengthen employees' organizational identification. One of the most effective ways to increase organizational identification is to ensure that employees are in harmony with the mission and vision of the organization (Dutton et al., 1994). The organization should clearly define its values and develop strategies to unite its employees around these values. In this process, including employees in the decision-making systems of the organization and making them feel valuable will reinforce their sense of belonging (Eisenberger, Huntington & Hutchison, 1986). Leadership style is also very important in organizational identification. Supportive and employee-oriented leaders help employees to establish stronger ties with the organization (Bartels, Pruyn, De Jong & Joustra, 2007). Encouraging open communication, giving regular feedback to employees and appreciating their contributions contribute to increased organizational identification. In addition, increasing the perception of organizational support will help employees to feel valued by the organization (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

What to Do to Reduce Presenteeism

When employees continue to come to work despite being ill or psychologically exhausted, it is defined as presenteeism (Johns, 2010). This situation not only decreases individual productivity but may also negatively affect organizational performance in the long run. To prevent presenteeism, organizations need to create a culture that cares about employee health. In this regard, effective implementation of health and welfare programs is of great importance. Programs should be developed to protect both the physical and mental health of employees (Lu, Lin, & Cooper, 2013). Providing ergonomic working conditions, offering psychological support services and encouraging regular health check-ups ensure

that employees are in a healthy work environment. In addition, employees' work should be distributed fairly and rest periods should be adequate (Aronsson & Gustafsson, 2005). Flexible working models should be adopted so that employees do not feel obliged to come to work despite their health problems (Miraglia & Johns, 2016). Remote or hybrid working models allow employees to manage their work processes more efficiently (Gosselin, Lemyre & Corneil, 2013). Managers monitoring their employees' health status and encouraging them to rest when necessary is an important factor in preventing presenteeism (Demerouti et al., 2009). Providing a safe working environment within the organization can support both psychological and physical health of employees by reducing their anxiety and stress levels (Hansen & Andersen, 2008).

What to Do to Increase Psychological Ownership

Psychological ownership is the development of a strong sense of belonging to one's organization and work (Pierce et al., 2001). Employees' emotional investment in their jobs is an important factor that increases both their job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Van Dyne & Pierce, 2004). Therefore, organizations need to adopt practices that will encourage psychological ownership in employees. Employees having a say in business processes is one of the main factors that support the development of psychological ownership (Avey et al., 2009). Participation in decision-making processes gives employees a sense of control over work processes and thus increases their organizational commitment. Providing employees with meaningful and valuable tasks helps them develop a stronger sense of ownership towards their work (Mayhew et al., 2007). When individuals are aware of the results of their work and feel that they contribute to organizational goals, they exhibit higher levels of psychological ownership. Managers' supportive attitude towards employees is a factor that strengthens this process (Dawkins, Tian, Newman & Martin, 2017). Investing in the development of employees will increase their sense of belonging to the organization and will enable them to show more commitment to work processes. In addition, creating open communication channels within the organization and creating an environment where employees can freely express their views are among the factors that support the development of a sense of psychological ownership (Brown, Crossley & Robinson, 2014). Strengthening social relations within the organization can also increase employees' organizational commitment and ownership. Therefore, organizational managers should pay attention to all these issues.

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